

RESULTS OF IMPLANTATION OF DIFFERENT MODELS OF INTRAOCULAR LENSES IN CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL CATARACTS

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Abstract. *The given article presents the results of implantation of various models of intraocular lenses in children with congenital cataracts. The total number of children diagnosed with congenital cataracts was 57 (67 eyes). Results of the analysis of the clinical and functional state of the visual organ were selected from children during the period from 2022 to 2023. The purpose of the study is the analysis of the results of surgical treatment of congenital cataracts in children and the dynamics of secondary cataract development depending on the implantation of hydrophobic and hydrophilic IOLs. Complications after surgery were observed in 31 cases.*

Keywords: *congenital cataract, intraocular lens, hydrophobic, hydrophilic, complications.*

Introduction. Congenital cataracts (CC) still occupy a significant place in the structure of blindness and visual impairment and are one of the main causes of visual disability in children [1, 2]. The given article presents the results of implantation of various models of intraocular lenses in children with congenital cataracts. The total number of children was 57 (67 eyes) with a diagnosis of congenital cataract. The results of the analysis of the clinical and functional state of the visual organ were taken from children for the period from 2022 to 2023. The results of implantation of various IOL models were evaluated in accordance with the presence of secondary cataract after implantation. Secondary cataracts developed more often in the eyes with a hydrophilic IOL of the type of ASPHIRE, when the indicators of secondary cataracts with hydrophobic lenses were the lowest.

Research aim. Analysis of the results of surgical treatment of congenital cataracts in children and the dynamics of secondary cataract development depending on the implantation of hydrophobic and hydrophilic IOLs.

Relevance. Congenital cataracts are one of the main causes of blindness. This issue remains significant today, as the quality of primary surgical intervention determines the long-term condition of the aphakic patient—an artificial eye for many years of life, affecting both children and adults. This, in turn, impacts the quality of life, social adaptation within families, and communities. To date, surgery remains the only method for treating cataracts. The first implantation of an intraocular lens (IOL) in children was performed in the early 1950s by E. Epstein and P. Choyce (Great Britain). Intraocular correction in children with congenital cataracts presents a complex challenge, particularly in very young children (7-8 months), due to pronounced clinical and functional variability, age-related anatomical and physiological features of the eye, and the presence of associated congenital eye conditions. The optimal condition for stable intracapsular fixation of IOLs in a child's growing eye is the preservation of a reliable capsule bag

with the posterior capsule intact. IOL implantation is a clear advantage over eyeglass or contact lens correction, as it eliminates isiconia, contributing to high visual function and the restoration of binocular vision. Cataract surgery in children has advanced significantly in recent decades. Congenital cataracts are now detected at earlier stages, and small incision surgery, which does not require stitches and accounts for astigmatism, is increasingly popular. Modern research indicates that the use of IOLs alleviates many issues and contributes positively to the development of a child's eye. Recent data even suggest the safety and effectiveness of IOLs for newborns. However, many issues in pediatric cataract surgery remain under discussion. A key feature of cataract surgery in young children is that the eye has not yet completed its development at the time of surgery, complicating the calculation of intraocular lenses and affecting the choice of surgical technique. While there are nomograms for calculating IOLs in children, their application is often limited to standard cases. In practice, various factors must be considered, including the patient's age, the bilaterality of cataracts, the presence of amblyopia, potential difficulties with glasses or contact lenses, hereditary factors, concurrent systemic and ophthalmological conditions, and the social and educational levels of parents.

Materials and Methods: The examination of patients in the ophthalmology department of TashPMI clinic included 57 patients (67 eyes) with congenital cataracts, comprising 29 boys and 28 girls. The patients' ages ranged from 3 months to 16 years. From 2022 to 2023, all patients underwent operations for congenital cataract extraction with the implantation of soft hydrophobic and hydrophilic intraocular lenses (IOLs), including models such as "Truefold SAPPHIRE" (India), "Acrysof IQ" (Alcon, USA), "880 UV," and "867 UV" (USIOL, USA). These lenses, made from hydrophilic and hydrophobic acrylic, differ in design features. The Truefold SAPPHIRE IOL has an optical part with diameters ranging from 2.2 to 3.7 mm, depending on the model, and features doubled support elements for fixation in the capsule bag. The Acrysof IQ IOL has a 6.0 mm diameter monoblock biconvex aspherical structure. The model "880 UV" is also hydrophilic with a 6.0 mm optical part, similar to the Truefold SAPPHIRE. The model "867 UV" shares a design with "880 UV" but includes double support elements. For the implantation of these IOL models, a corneoscleral or corneal tunnel incision of 2.8 mm was made, allowing lens insertion via an injector. The patient examination included visometry, biomicroscopy, ophthalmoscopy, and ultrasound A/V scanning.

Results and Discussions: All patients underwent cataract surgery under combined endotracheal anesthesia (CATN). Congenital cataract extraction was performed on 57 patients. In 21 cases (31.34%), Truefold lenses were implanted; in 29 cases (43.28%), Acrysof IQ Alcon IOLs were used; in 14 cases (20.89%), "880 UV" lenses were implanted; and in 3 cases (4.49%), "867 UV" lenses were used. Before surgery, visual function assessments showed that 25 patients had light perception with correct projection, while 32 children had visual acuity ranging from 0.01 to 0.1.

What is more important, in young children, vision was assessed by indirect signs such as gaze fixation and tracking movement. Surgical intervention resulted in significant improvement in visual acuity for most patients. Implantation of Acrysof IQ IOLs led to visual acuity improvements: from 0.01 to 0.09 in 8 patients, from 0.1 to 0.3 in 9 children, and from 0.4 to 0.7 in 12 patients. The use of USIOLs resulted in improved vision for 5 patients from 0.02 to 0.09, for 9 patients from 0.1 to 0.3, and for 3 patients from 0.2 to 0.7. TrueFold lens implantation resulted in visual acuity increases to 0.01–0.09 in 11 patients, to 0.1–0.3 in 4 children, and up to 0.4–0.7 in 6

patients. In the postoperative period (up to 6 months), complications included fibrin reaction in 9 cases (13.4%) and "pupil capture" syndrome in 7 cases (10.44%).

Besides that, secondary cataract developed more frequently in patients with hydrophilic IOLs—15 cases (22.39%)—while secondary cataracts were observed in only 3 patients (4.48%) with hydrophobic IOLs. Laser capsulotomy is recommended for treating these complications. Based on these observations, we conclude that hydrophobic IOLs from Acrysof IQ and USIOL are optimal for implantation in children with congenital cataracts, as they significantly reduce the risk of secondary cataracts due to their design features.

Conclusion: Our observations indicate that hydrophobic intraocular lenses (IOLs) manufactured by Acrysof IQ and USIOL demonstrate high effectiveness when implanted in children with congenital cataracts. Their use significantly reduces the risk of developing secondary cataracts compared to hydrophilic IOLs. This advantage stems from the design features of hydrophobic lenses, such as increased biocompatibility and material resistance to prolonged contact with ocular tissues.

By summarizing it should be suggested that hydrophobic acrylic lenses have a lower tendency to form cellular deposits on the posterior capsule, thus reducing the likelihood of fibrotic changes and secondary cataracts. Therefore, hydrophobic IOLs are the optimal choice for long-term optical correction in children after congenital cataract extraction, providing stable results and reducing the frequency of postoperative complications.

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